

UNDERSTANDING GOOD PRACTICE IN THE DIGITAL TRANSFER PROCESS BY CONNECTING WITH THE DIGITAL PRESERVATION COMMUNITY

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Abstract – This poster explores collaborative work by the University of Sheffield and the Digital Preservation Coalition which explored what good practice looks like for the digital transfer process. We use the term “Digital Transfer” to refer to the means by which born-digital or digitised content is given to an Archive from a donor or depositor (either an individual or an organisation). This is also referred to as a “deposit”. A digital transfer can be from an external or internal donor to an organisation.

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I. BACKGROUND TO THE PROBLEM

The University of Sheffield had concerns about its processing and procedure for digital transfers to its Archives. There was no standard method for donors to transfer digital content to the Archives, and staff at the University frequently received collections with very little associated context or metadata.

There was uncertainty in how content should safely be transferred from a donor's computer onto university servers, raising technical questions such as:

- Should content be transferred to an external media carrier first?

- Should content be transferred over the Cloud?
- What are the implications to the digital assets or the metadata in doing so?

In terms of documentation, the University did not provide donors with guidance on transfer process, and explain how the transfer should happen. There was no guidance which detailed which preservation actions are undertaken to ensure on-going access to digital assets, or what permissions are required for providing access to this content in different ways.

Understanding the importance of working with donors with varying technical abilities, whilst also minimizing the risk of changes to data and metadata, the University was concerned about whether their current processes aligned with digital preservation good practice, indeed whether they were even ‘good enough’. To initiate a collaborative exploration of this topic with the wider community they contacted the Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) for support.

II. METHODOLOGY

In order to address the questions and challenges identified by the University of Sheffield, and in particular, answer the question ‘what does good practice look like for the deposit or transfer process?’ it was agreed that a helpful approach would be to

bring together digital preservation community members to discuss this topic and share their thoughts.

In late 2024 the DPC put out a message to its members asking for volunteers to join a focus group to discuss how the deposit and transfer process works for them. This turned out to be a popular topic with 35 people expressing an interest in being involved. We set up two focus groups in February 2025, scheduled to allow participation from different time zones.

The focus groups had representation from a range of institutions, including national bodies, specialist repositories, and universities. Mentimeter was used to collect responses to the questions posed, but discussion was also encouraged, and attendees were generous in sharing their knowledge and experience as well as links to their own guidance and processes where they could.

As well as 'what does good practice look like for the deposit or transfer process?', we also asked several questions about how transfer of digital content works in practice.

III. FINDINGS

Analysing the results from these focus group discussions and follow on work at the University of Sheffield are still in progress but a few key findings were immediately apparent.

Firstly, the answer to the question 'what does good practice look like for the deposit or transfer process?' is highly dependent on the context of the organization receiving the digital content. It was clear there was no one-size-fits-all approach and a variety of practices were discussed throughout the sessions.

Deposit and transfer processes and workflows seem largely to have evolved from the ground up, changing and adapting to different circumstances. Even within each organization, there was often no single process that would be followed in all cases. Participants talked about the journey they took with different depositors - evolving and adapting their processes and list of requirements depending on who they were working with. The level of skill and understanding of individual depositors was discussed and it was noted that being flexible and adaptable was necessary, rather than having a rigid approach that may be off-putting or technically

demanding and may ultimately lead to relationships with depositors breaking down.

Whilst each new deposit or transfer may offer a slightly new challenge, one helpful idea from the focus groups was to have an internal checklist that staff within the archive can use to help guide their conversations with potential donors and depositors. It can be a careful balance - so knowing which questions to ask, but also what the archive can live without if necessary.

Good practice in the digital transfer process is about being able to demonstrate that the integrity of the digital content has been preserved throughout the process and ensuring that you have adequate documentation and metadata to understand that content going forward. Conversations within the focus groups did touch on tools and transfer methodologies that can help with the more technical challenges of digital transfer. It was clear however that soft skills, such as good communication and careful negotiation, were equally important. In the words of one participant "*so much is about relationships rather than the deposit process alone*".

IV. CONCLUSION

This collaborative work has brought us closer to an understanding of what good practice looks like for the digital deposit and transfer process. As with many topics in digital preservation, there is no single answer to this question and practices vary depending on the context of the organization involved as well as any number of variables. There are however some areas where consensus was reached, and this poster will provide an opportunity to share these with the wider community.

Author Biographies

Bryony Hooper is the Digital Preservation Manager at the University of Sheffield and Co-founder of DigiPres North.

Jenny Mitcham is the Chief Digital Preservation Officer at the Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC). She works with members of the Coalition to understand their digital preservation challenges and tailor DPC activities and support to their needs.

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